

DMS Impact Survey

This survey aims to assess the efficacy and impact of the Data Market Services programme.

Your responses will be used to fine tune the services that we offer, as well as helping us to demonstrate the wider economic and social outcomes of our programme to the European Commission. This will help public funders to understand why DMS makes a difference and hopefully continue to fund similar programmes in the future.

Your input is extremely important to us!

* Required

1. Your name *

2. Your email address *

3. Your company name *

Service
evaluation

We are interested to know about the specific ways in which DMS services have impacted your business, as well as the skills and knowledge gained by your team.

4. BUSINESS: Please rate these business activities according to how much they benefited from your participation in DMS *

Mark only one oval per row.

	1 - benefited least	2	3	4	5 - benefited most
Promoting your company	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Fundraising	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Upskilling your workforce	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Data compliance management	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
IP management	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Entrepreneurial skills	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Exploring international markets	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

5. SKILLS: How much did your team's skills improve in each of these categories? *

Mark only one oval per row.

	1 - no improvement	2	3	4	5 - excellent improvement
Promoting your company	<input type="radio"/>				
Fundraising	<input type="radio"/>				
Entrepreneurship	<input type="radio"/>				
Data science & AI	<input type="radio"/>				
Data standardisation	<input type="radio"/>				
Compliance & GDPR	<input type="radio"/>				
IP management	<input type="radio"/>				

Market impact

Your sales capacity

Sales capacity refers to your ability to serve new clients. This can include improved efficiency in logistics, human resources or utilisation of new technical assets.

6. Has the sales capacity of your company increased since joining DMS? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

7. If yes, please provide the estimated increase in % and specify what has improved.

8. Did you gain any new clients as a result of joining DMS? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

9. If yes, how many?

10. Could you name one way DMS has helped you increase your market impact?

Fundraising

11. Have you gained any additional funding since starting DMS? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

12. If yes, please specify the amount, public or private, and number of rounds

13. Could you name one way DMS has helped you increase your fundraising abilities?

Innovation

14. Have you developed any new products, datasets or services since joining DMS?

*

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

15. If yes, please specify the type of solution (e.g. dataset, cloud service, mobile app), and whether you applied for IPR (e.g. patent, trademark)

16. Could you name one way DMS has helped you increase your innovation capacity?

Social Impact

17. Has your team grown since you joined DMS? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

18. If yes, please tell us how many new members have joined your team and their position/role within your company

19. Has the gender composition of your team changed since joining the programme? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

20. If yes, please give us a % breakdown of before/after. (e.g. Before 75% female, 25% male. After 60% female, 40% male)

21. Have you pursued any new collaborations or partnerships? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

22. Could you name one way DMS has helped you increase your social impact?

Your Success

23. Would you like to share a success story or testimonial so that we can help give you visibility?

24. How likely are you to recommend DMS to other startups? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Not likely	<input type="radio"/>	Extremely likely				

25. Looking back on your experience at DMS, is there anything we could have done better to support your business?

Thank you very much for completing this survey, we appreciate your response!

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